

D2.4 Second use guideline

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Executive summary

Report on guidelines and strategy for circular economy approach regarding second use and dismantling activities.

The report is divided in 4 sections covering:

- 1) The analysis of pathways taken by the EV batteries until they reach the end of their first life
- 2) The status of those batteries when 2nd life is initiated
- 3) The different applications that can be considered for the 2nd life batteries
- 4) The remanufacturing considerations estimated necessary to be able to use those batteries by refurbishing new ones if required

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List of abbreviations

<i>BP</i>	<i>Battery Pack</i>
<i>CE</i>	<i>Circular Economy</i>
<i>DoD</i>	<i>Depth of Discharge</i>
<i>EoL</i>	<i>End of Life</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicle</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>SoH</i>	<i>State of Health</i>
<i>SoC</i>	<i>State of Charge</i>
<i>BMS</i>	<i>Battery Management System</i>
<i>LCA</i>	<i>Life Cycle Analysis</i>
<i>SoP</i>	<i>State of Power</i>
<i>PV</i>	<i>Photovoltaic</i>
<i>LIB</i>	<i>Lithium-Ion Battery</i>

Introduction

This report covers the guidelines and strategy for circular economy approach regarding second use and dismantling activities.

The report is divided in 4 sections covering:

- 1) The analysis of pathways taken by the EV batteries until they reach the end of their first life.
- 2) The status of those batteries when 2nd life is initiated.
- 3) The different applications that can be considered for the 2nd life batteries.
- 4) The remanufacturing considerations estimated necessary to be able to use those batteries by refurbishing new ones if required.

1. EV battery EoL circuit

In this chapter we will describe the pathways that Electric Vehicle (EV) batteries follow to reach the End of life (EoL).

There are several ways in which an EV battery can reach its EoL, among the main drivers that lead to finishing the battery use in first life (use as an EV) the following are highlighted:

- Vehicle crash/accident: the vehicle, including the battery, is severely damaged and for safety reasons neither the battery or spare parts can be re-used
- Vehicle replacement: the vehicle is not old enough to be retired but the owner decides to replace it with a new vehicle. The battery SoH is high and the performance is still good, however, for several reasons a new model is acquired
- Vehicle underperforming: Depending on the application and use of the vehicle it is possible that high levels of battery degradation that lead to dissatisfaction of the owner since the EV is not meeting the expected performance. This is more likely in the case of commercial users that require a long driving distance (i.e., energy demand) or transport heavy goods (i.e., power demand), but is also possible with non-commercial users, depending on user needs.
- Vehicle broken: The vehicle is damaged beyond repair or is too expensive to be fixed but the battery is still in good condition.
- Vehicle old: The vehicle has reached its warranty lifespan. Even though it may have low mileage, the calendar aging puts the battery into a low SoH region.

In Fig. 1 the distribution of this EoL drivers and rough approximation of their SoH is provided. According to [1], EV batteries generally have a lifespan of 8 years, however, it appears that EV batteries can last much longer than originally predicted. A small number of EV batteries will reach their EoL sooner than 8 years as a result of battery failure or vehicle collisions, these are estimated at about 1% to 3% of the EV stock based on discussions with industry representatives.

The concept of failure can be assessed by criteria such as performance (performing at an unsatisfactory level), functionality (incapable of performing a specific function) and availability (machine breakdowns). Nonetheless, the basic concepts of how an EoL event should be specified are not clear, especially in systems with nonlinear degradation behaviours such as lithium-ion secondary batteries (LIBs).

In [2] the results have shown that the EoL is dependent on the battery characteristics as well as on the application specifications. The ranges of resistance increase and capacity decrease that lead to the EoL vary greatly between applications. The commonly assumed 70–80% relative capacity EoL threshold is too optimistic for the high-energy EV application (the EoL event happens before reaching 87%); and both, the 200% relative resistance and 70–80% relative capacity as EoL threshold are still far from defining the real EoL event in the high-power EV application (the EoL event is not reached even at a combination of 400% relative resistance and 60% relative capacity).

In fact, a study of vehicle disposal shows that even within Europe, car average lifespan goes from less than 10 years in Belgium to almost 20 in Spain and Portugal [3]. EV battery replacement does not correspond to failure but to its degradation according to its use. These concepts are close but they are not the same thing, as EVs may still satisfy an owner’s needs even though they reached the accepted 80% SoH EoL criteria [4].

According to the SoH of batteries after collection, different second life opportunities and their share were obtained [5]. Around 10% of recovered batteries (SoH>88%) will return into the automotive industry as spare parts or replacement batteries; close to 70% of the remanufactured batteries will end up in high-capacity installations including providing grid services, for residential use, or in hybrid trucks or electric boats. Finally, 20% of batteries (SoH>75%) could be dismantled into modules and cells to prepare new remanufactured batteries to be used for low-capacity demanding systems, smaller applications, such as electric bicycles or assisting robots.

Figure 1. Paths followed by EV batteries to reach EoL

2. SoH status of EV batteries

This chapter describes the SoH of batteries that reach EoL based on statistics and studies.

In recent years, the demand of batteries has increased with the growth of portable applications. It is widely known that the performance of batteries decreases with time and use. This loss of performance is measured by the State-of-Health (SoH) of the cells. The SoH is a figure of merit that indicates the battery level of degradation [6,7]. Due to the complex nonlinear behaviour of the battery, estimating battery SoH can be very challenging. Estimating the battery SoH in real time is very important for automotive applications. It allows battery fault diagnosis and help prevent hazardous accidents. It provides accurate knowledge on the battery performance that can help manage the energy distribution in HEV and improve their consumption and lifetime [8].

Most of all the real time SoH estimation allows an accurate estimation of the battery SoC (State-of-Charge) and SoP (State-of-Power). Additionally, it can be useful in terms of maintenance and replacement schedules. However, there is no consensus on how to best define this parameter. Experimental, theoretical, and even heuristic approaches can be found in literature and in use with commercial systems, but usually, they are only appropriate for particular conditions and some of them are not linked to the degradation suffered by the cells themselves [19].

The United State Council for Automotive Research LLC (USCAR) developed testing procedures and criterion for determining the SoH of EV batteries. In general, as per the USCAR's USABC (United States Advanced Battery Consortium) manual, an end-of-life condition is reached when the device is no longer able to meet the defined targets which are evaluated based on the periodic Reference Performance Tests, particularly the HPPC and Peak Power test results. As per the USABC manual, when the power and energy performance of the device degrades to the point that there is no power or energy margin (i.e., Available Energy is less than the target value at the target power), the device has reached EoL. In addition, the inability to meet any of the other USABC technical targets such as the Self-discharge target, also constitutes EoL. A recent study consisted of a thorough review of the contemporary battery SoH estimation methods and concluded that model-based methods (which use models that describe battery behavior considering SoH indicators which are identified to estimate battery states and their performances) due to their accuracy and compatibility with on-board and online applications, present the most satisfying accuracy in terms of real time SoH indicator identification [20].

While conducting environmental analysis of EVs, most of the Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) are performed considering that vehicles will be driven from 100,000 to nearly 250,000 km [9]. Many of those studies try to in some way align with the warranties given by car manufacturers, which are typically from 8 to 10 years within this range of mileage [10], keeping the overall mileage around 150.000 km [11]. This value is, incidentally, also aligned with the expected lifespan of batteries for traction purposes. Batteries degrade over time whether they are used or not. Degradation is caused by many factors including temperature, intensity of use, depth-of-discharge (DOD), working voltage, and time (used or not) [12]. It is generally accepted that the battery is not appropriate for mobility purposes when its State-of-Health (SoH) reaches 70–80% of its initial capacity [13]. After this point, the battery is considered to be at End-of-Life (EoL). Then, these batteries are either sent to recycle or they are re-used in stationary applications offering them a second life, as most car manufacturers are starting to evaluate and test [14,15]. Therefore, this point of EoL is largely influenced and determined by the car manufacturers, who have generally accepted this aforementioned 70-80% of original battery energy capacity as a SoH limit norm for EoL. LCA studies on EVs hence should identify and concretely establish the boundary of the study before performing the environmental analysis. This an important first task and can have an influence on the acceptable second life applications.

Casals, et. al (2019) indicated through their results that the EoL of 80% SoH might be mostly acceptable for small capacity EVs (16 kWh); however, for medium-duty and higher capacity EVs (24 and 30 kWh) the EoL of 80% SoH is likely an overestimate. It was shown that the SoH could

go below 60% without having a noticeable impact on daily mobility as more than 99% of trips are still achievable even with severely aged batteries [16].

Although the capacity decrease does not create a limitation in daily electric mobility, there are other aspects that can have an impact on mobility. One is the exponential increase of the internal resistance of the battery with aging. In fact, the internal resistance at 80% SoH increases only by 20% while at 60% SoH it goes up to 200% [17], which might create additional losses on power and on efficiency. The other aspect is that, beyond the 60% SoH, the chances to fall into the aging knee (a sudden acceleration of battery aging) increase dramatically, considerably shortening the expected lifespan after this point [18].

EV owners also play a crucial role when considering SoH at EoL of their EVs. For instance, if they are informed of the current SoC of the battery, they are capable of modifying their behavior to avoid taking trips where they would be unable to reach the final destination, hence altering the energy consumption pattern of their EV's battery. This has also been highlighted in results from a previous study which indicated that delayed charging and lower utilization of fast chargers have the potential to reduce the rate of battery degradation. While the utilization of fast chargers and delayed charging can have an impact on battery health and can be implemented with the use of smart chargers, user-oriented incentives without impacting drivers' mobility needs, there are other elements, for example depth of discharge (DoD), that also have a significant impact on battery health but because they are tied to the driver's basic mobility needs (e.g., trip distance) they are more difficult to affect [21].

3. Options for 2nd life batteries

In this chapter the different options and application for used EV batteries are described

3.1 Introduction

Although EV batteries at the end of their useful life for electric vehicle are no longer adapted to supply power to demanding motors such as cars, most of them still retain 50 to 80% of their capacity. The initial cost of second-life batteries is attractive, even considering the lower prices of electrical storage technologies; The cost of a reused battery is calculated around 50 € / kWh, compared to 200-300 € for new systems, estimating to remain competitive at least until 2025, when the price of a new battery should reach 90 €/ kWh.

Applications that are less demanding than mobility, such as stationary storage systems, are promising options for taking advantage of the saved value of used batteries. In such applications, the old batteries are expected to be able to provide service for an additional ten years. In this sense, the first generations of used vehicle batteries are already being tested for various purposes around the world, such as in applications for the management of demand peaks or the regulation of the frequency of the network.

¹Eg, improve grid performance, integrate renewables, charge EVs, etc.
Source: Expert interviews; market research reports; McKinsey analysis

Figure 2. Decision Support System concept for determining the optimal 2nd-life batteries.
(Source: Second-life EV batteries: The newest value pool in energy storage". Mckinsey, 2019)

According to the conceptual scheme of Figure 2, there are 3 main destinations for used batteries (end of first life):

- A. Rejection
- B. Second life or reuse applications
- C. Recovery of components and metals or Recycling

In this section, the different types of scenarios for option B are defined, that is, the different 2nd-life applications. In addition, the analysis to identify the main technical requirements of each second life application, from the point of view of technical specifications, will be considering. The main technical requirements to be studied are:

- The maximum charging current
- The maximum discharge current
- The nominal capacity required for the storage system
- The range of working voltages
- The operating conditions from the point of view of temperature and humidity
- The storage capacity
- Energy density
- Response time
- Energy efficiency

This information can be used by the decision support system (DSS) to define the restrictions on the use of the battery according to its status and applications. Energy Storage technologies have a wide range of uses and numerous classification approaches are possible.

To categorize all potential applications for electrical storage batteries can be a very complex task depending on the classification logic used. In fact, there are two most common classification logics in the literature, but the number of applications within these publications can vary. A first common classification is based on a logistical perspective of the electricity system, classifying the applications along the electricity value chain. The other classification is based on a parametric perspective, classifying applications based on their technical requirements, usually in terms of nominal power and storage capacity, but response time is also important. There is an alternative presentation for parametric classification logic in which applications are classified into power or energy applications, with nominal power being the most relevant technical requirement for the former and storage capacity for the latter.

Based on the latest research studies on 2nd-life battery applications, ten specific applications have been selected and are divided into two groups following a logistical perspective: five applications at global generation level or distribution network level and five applications at end-user level.

3.2 Classification criteria

Mainly three key performance parameters will be examined and compared: thermal response, efficiency, and energy density. It must be considered that the expected or available remaining useful life of a 2nd-life battery is another important consideration that is outside the scope of this classification but serves to classify batteries that are not suitable for a 2nd use.

3.2.1 Location and Thermal response

The first important initial criterion for 2nd-life battery classification is the location of the battery where it will be reused. It is related to the thermal response parameter. In this case, three cases have been defined with their temperature requirements, divided into northern or colder countries, temperate countries, or tropical or dry areas. The ideal thermal response comparison would involve increasing the frequency regulation power multiplier in subsequent tests until each battery reaches a high temperature safety limit. However, this is not feasible, since active thermal management batteries experience little thermal build-up even at high power multipliers. Instead, an approximate thermal response metric τ is calculated for each battery based on Equation $\tau = (T_{limit} - T_{ambient}) - (T_{peak} - T_{ref})$ (1):

$$\tau = (T_{limit} - T_{ambient}) - (T_{peak} - T_{ref}) \quad (1)$$

Where T_{limit} is the battery limit safety temperature, $T_{ambient}$ is the ambient temperature, T_{peak} is the maximum battery temperature measured during the cycle and T_{ref} is the reference temperature defined as the average temperature of the thermal management fluid measured during the cycle. Equation $\tau = (T_{limit} - T_{ambient}) - (T_{peak} - T_{ref})$ (1) compares the maximum allowed battery temperature increment above ambient temperature to the maximum battery temperature increment measured during the test. A high value of τ indicates that heat is being rejected to maintain the safe operating temperature, while $\tau = 0$ indicates that the safe temperature limit has been reached. To compare batteries tested with a different T_{ref} , it is assumed that batteries tested with $T_{ref} \neq T_{ambient}$ would have experienced the same temperature change if they had been tested with $T_{ref} = T_{ambient}$.

It is a fact that batteries work best at room temperature, and any drift towards hot or cold changes causes a variation in their performance and longevity. For this reason, the location is classified by zones applying the Köppen climatic classification, simplifying to four zones (A, C, D and E) and with the following parameters based on ambient temperatures:

Figure 3. Köppen classification according to maximum and minimum temperatures

- Northern zones: include cold (D) or polar (E) areas. Their average temperatures are:

$$T_{avg. hot - E zone} < 10 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_{avg. cold - D zone} < -3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_{avg. hot - D zone} > 10 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

- Temperate zones: include the temperate areas (C). Their average colder temperatures are:

$$-3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C} < T_{avg. cold - C zone} < 18 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

- Tropical or dry zones: include dry or arid areas and tropical areas (A) such as deserts or jungles. Their average colder temperatures are:

$$T_{avg. cold - A zone} > 18 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

By means of this first climatic classification, the thermal response parameter calculated with Equation $\tau = (T_{limit} - T_{ambient}) - (T_{peak} - T_{ref})$ (1 and the pertinent tests, it will be important to determine by means of DSS if the location (*Figure 4*) is suitable for the placement of certain types of batteries.

Figure 4. World map of climates according to the Köppen climate classification. Source: Pill, M.C., Philyson, B.L, McMahon, T.E. (2007). Updated global map of the Koppem climate classification, Earth Sciences and Hydrology, 11, 1644-1633.

3.2.2 Electricity market and energy efficiency

The second criterion for 2nd-life battery classification is the type of electricity market in the country where the batteries will be placed, totally related to the efficiency of the battery. High energy efficiency for an energy storage system in most applications reduces the amount of energy required to maintain State of Charge (SOC), thereby reducing the electricity consumption of the system (*i.e.* lower operational costs). The amount of waste heat generated is also reduced, which makes it possible to increase the frequency regulation service offering or to improve the energy quality and reliability in the network (higher revenues), in addition to reducing the thermal management loads (*i.e.* lower exploitation costs).

Specifically, for this criterion it will be necessary to know the electricity price that will be consumed, or its variable part (*i.e.* the energy costs), instead of the power costs (fixed costs), since the savings through a high energy efficiency battery will reduce energy but will not affect the contracted power. *Figure 5* shows the worldwide price distribution, contributed by IEA (2020), that allows a first vision to establish an electricity price measurement scale in MARBEL.

Figure 5. Worldwide distribution of the electricity price (USD / MWh). Source: IEA (2020), Energy Prices 2020, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-prices-2020>

The electricity purchase prices classification levels shown in Figure 6 are based on the 25th and 75th percentiles for the normal distribution according to the electricity price.

Figure 6. Worldwide distribution (# countries) according to electricity price (USD / MWh)

From this, one can obtain:

- Low electricity price (P1): 25th percentile of the normal distribution, where it is less than 120 USD / MWh (ca. 0.10 € / kWh) of electricity.
- Moderate electricity price (P2): between the 25th and 75th percentile, where it is between USD 120 / MWh and USD 180 / MWh (between ca. 0.10 € / kWh and ca. 0.15 € / kWh) of electricity.
- High electricity price (P3): 75th percentile of the normal distribution, where it is greater than 180 USD / MWh (ca. 0.15 € / kWh) of electricity.

Figure 7. Electricity price per country in USD/MWh

Figure 7 shows both Residential and Industrial electricity prices for some countries. Considering the Low-Moderate-High classification, 9 zones (PS) can be defined depending on their end-use. Thus, It also allows to observe which countries give greater importance to the industry and to price regulation *i.e.* a price reduction to greater consumers, such as Spain, Germany, Japan or the United States.

It is recommended to group the 9 zones according to the first classification (P1, P2 or P3), and although a linear regression with a slope centered at the point $(x, y) = (0,0)$ is observed, there are anomalous values in the zones PS1, PS3, PS4 and PS6. Therefore, it will be advisable to define in what type or for what type of consumers the batteries will be installed. Since the price for residential electricity and for the industrial sector is very different in most countries, it is critical the need to consider a concrete area in order to ascertain its definitive 2nd-life battery application.

3.2.3 Environmental aspects: carbon footprint and energy density

The third initial criterion is the evaluation of the environmental aspects related to the application of second life batteries, and in particular carbon footprint or materials consumptions/savings generated by the 2nd-life battery. These environmental aspects may have place in the different steps to convert a battery that ends its first life in the vehicle in a second life object (for instance, the removal of the battery from the vehicle, the testing to determine the SoH, the battery disassembling and the location or by the area location or the occupied space that is required due to their large volume and to their materials density.

This criterion is clearly related to, one side, the energy consumed to prepare the battery for a second life (repurposing activities and testing) and, on the other hand, to the energy density of the batteries, measured in Wh / kg since, depending on the space available and the importance given to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions for the concrete installation that has a significant weight.

Regarding the energy consumption to prepare the battery to a second life, it is clear that this will be directly dependent on how easy the SoH and status of the battery can be determined, that will depend on the design of the battery and the modules and cells architecture. Furthermore, depending on the second life application and the SoH, the repurposing and disassembling activities to perform on the battery will determine the amount of energy required to obtain the modules or cells to be used in the second life. The deeper the disassembly is (to cells level, for instance), the higher the energy consumption and therefore the associated carbon footprint.

Regarding the energy density, although it may seem that higher energy density batteries should always be chosen for all types of applications, in practice this is not always true. Some long-range electric vehicle batteries, such as the Tesla Model S, are designed primarily for energy density at the expense of energy efficiency. In some utility grid storage environments with limited space for batteries (such as the commonly used 40ft shipping container), a fixed volume with higher storage capacity (higher service offering for grid regulation) and less Round-trip energy efficiency (higher electricity consumption) can generate a higher economic return than the opposite. In an off-grid energy storage environment with non-critical dimensions (such as a large warehouse), energy density may be the most important factor.

Modules with high energy density store approximately twice as much energy per unit volume as other types of battery modules. In practice, the installation developer or its designer must consider space limitations when selecting 2nd-life batteries for electric vehicles for grid applications. As an initial classification it can be differentiated two types of facilities with a binary factor:

- Important carbon footprint (1): where the space for battery placement is reduced and the energy density is to be maximized.
- Carbon footprint not so important (0): where the space for battery placement is extensive and modules and energy density is to be minimized.

3.2.4 Scenario Comparison

The normalized scores for the above aspects illustrate the strengths and weaknesses of 2nd-life EV batteries based on individual performance metrics. The relative importance of these 3 metrics is specific to 2nd-life battery projects based on factors such as physical space, target market, and ambient temperature.

For a given project, a weighting value between 0 and 1 can be applied to each of the three performance scores shown in the previous section (thermal response, energy efficiency, and energy density) according to the relative importance of these performance metrics in the specific project. Averaging these three weighted scores yields a combined performance score out of 100, representing the relative performance value of each battery for the given project.

Note that the performance scores represent a weighting vector like the following [1: 0: 0], where it indicates the value of the thermal response, energy efficiency and energy density respectively.

Use cases where thermal response is less important could be projects where ambient temperature can be used effectively for thermal management (for example, a cold Nordic environment).

The scenario [1:0:1] represents the limit where energy efficiency is not considered while thermal response and energy density are weighted equally. In these use cases, projects could be included in electricity markets where the sale price of the grid service exceeds by far the purchase price of the electricity.

The scenario [1:1:0] represents the limit where energy density is not considered, while thermal response and energy efficiency are weighted equally. In these cases, projects where footprint is not a limitation (e.g. spacious industrial applications) could be included.

The scenario [1:1:1] represents the limit at which the three-performance metrics are valued equally. In these cases, with balanced weighting ratios, projects limited to a standard size storage container could be included in a hot southern climate with a volatile electricity market.

The ideal battery selection would require an economic analysis that includes additional factors such as battery model availability, current purchase prices of 2nd-life EV batteries, dynamics of the electricity market and the energy efficiency of the entire system considering auxiliary loads.

3.3 Specific applications

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of 2nd-life battery applications, showing how they are typically classified and highlighting some of the most relevant.

Storage technologies have a wide range of uses and numerous classification approaches are possible. In the particular case of electrical storage in batteries, the classification of all potential applications can be a very complex task depending on the classification logic used. A first common classification logic is based on the analog perspective of the electrical system, classifying the applications in the electricity value chain. The other classification is based on a parametric perspective based on their technical needs or requirements, usually in terms of power (commonly expressed in terms of discharge specifications), but also in terms of storage capacity.

There is an alternative introduction for parametric technology, with a classification logic in which applications are classified into power applications and energy applications, with energy being the most relevant technical requirement for the former and storage capacity for the latter. On the scientific basis of various publications and studies, ten applications for second-life batteries have been selected and divided into two groups, following a logistical criterion. Five applications at the generation or network level and five applications at the end-user level.

3.3.1 Electricity generation and Grid integration

3.3.1.1 Time shifting

Also known as energy arbitrage, in this application, electricity is stored in periods of lower electricity prices and is used or sold during peak hours or periods of peak demand. As a general idea, the technical requirements for this application are considerable storage capacity (1 to 100 MW) and moderate battery response times.

3.3.1.2 Stationary Energy Storage

This application can be described as storage over time, that is, where energy is stored over a very long period e.g. months. The technical requirements are similar to the previous case, but seasonal energy storage usually requires even more storage capacity and almost non-self-discharge losses.

3.3.1.3 Renewable energies integration

The goal of this application is to improve the use of renewable energy on a large scale. Therefore, as far as the application requirements are concerned, the nominal power must be compatible with the generation of electricity from renewable energy sources, which is why it usually tends of MW. The storage capacity must be able to cover time variations from minutes to several hours

and the battery response time must be fast enough to follow the variation rate of electrical power generation.

3.3.1.4 Transmission and Distribution

Transmission and distribution operators can use storage devices or batteries to improve executed operations, reducing grid stress and even postponing investments in maintenance. A few hundred MW of power, several hours of storage capacity, and a response time of a few minutes is sufficient for this application.

3.3.1.5 Grid regulation

This application includes the area, frequency, and voltage regulations of the electrical grid. The first two are related to the balance between supply and demand, which guarantees that the entire network is in good condition. The third provides support for reaction control at a more local level. The requirements of this application are a power of up to a few MW and a few minutes of storage capacity. The response time is the most relevant requirement since the device or battery must compensate for fluctuations in the network.

3.3.2 End-user

3.3.2.1 Energy/Power Management

Equivalent to the Time Shifting application, but from the end user level. While in the application of the previous section the stored energy is used to increase the electricity supply, here the stored energy is used to reduce the electricity demand in residential or tertiary facilities.

Figure 8. Example of a residential facility with batteries in Time Shifting mode

This application is also known as Time Shifting mode (see Figure 8), where it is used when the difference in rate between the peak and the valley is large enough.

3.3.2.2 Energy/Power Quality

This application counteracts the disturbances of the electrical network to maintain and guarantee a stable supply. Considering the application requirements, the power must be compatible with the end-user load capability, usually up to a maximum of one MW, but it can be scalable depending on the type of installation. A modest storage capacity is sufficient, but the most important requirement is the response time, which must be very fast, to compensate for fluctuations in the network.

3.3.2.3 Energy/Power Reliability (Back-up)

This application is intended to ensure power continuity during a power outage (see Figure 9). This throughput can be used in uninterruptible power supply (UPS) applications for industrial processes, data centers, and even healthcare facilities. The main requirements are that the power must be in line with the end-user load capability, which is usually tens of MW, and the storage capacity can vary from a few minutes to a few hours, depending on the required waiting time. Response time in these cases should be less than one second to quickly replenish the utility power supply.

This application is also known as Back-up mode and ensures that the battery will always have enough power in the event of a power outage. If renewable generation is available, it will first serve the battery and then the loads. In the case of not having renewable energy available, the system will charge the batteries directly from the grid. The inverter or controller will only take power from the battery in the event of an abnormal grid to power the loads.

Figure 9. Example of a residential scenario with batteries in Back-up mode

3.3.2.4 Integration of distributed renewable energies (Self-consumption)

The goal of this application is to increase the self-consumption rate of distributed generators, reducing demand, especially at peak times (see Figure 10). In this case, the technical requirements must be compatible with the power of distributed generation, which is usually up to hundreds of kW. A storage capacity of between 1 and 6 hours of range and a fast response time are two very important factors to follow the daily variation rate of renewable energy generation such as photovoltaic panels.

Figure 10. Example of a residential scenario with batteries in Self-consumption mode

This application is also known as self-consumption mode and is used in areas that have a high energy rate, but low re-injection. If renewable generation is available, it will power the load first and then the battery. If there is a surplus, it will be exported to the network. When renewable generation is no longer available or the power generated is not enough, the battery will first be discharged on the load and the grid will supply the missing.

3.3.2.5 e-Mobility Applications

This application is related to the supply of energy for electric vehicles. High energy density and high specific energy are the most important requirements for this application, but also the response time needs to be fast. In this specific case, some technologies that can produce fuels compatible with current technologies in the transport sector are also applicable in a holistic understanding of this application.

3.4 Technical requirements

This section will compile all the technical requirements for each 2nd-life battery application defined in the previous section. Specifically, Table 2 defines the power ratio (in MW or kW), the duration of the discharge as storage capacity, the approximate response time and other specific requirements or initial criteria for the implementation of batteries in each application.

In addition, before dividing it by application, it will be necessary to compare the requirements or minimum characteristics of conventional batteries according to the type of material used, placing emphasis on the Li-ion batteries previously used in the electric mobility sector and aligned with MARBEL project. This is specified in Table 1:

Battery technology	Power (MW)	Storage capacity		Response time	Self-discharge (%/day)	Full-charge duration	Efficiency (%)	Useful lifetime	
		Energy (MWh)	Disch. time					Years	Cycles @80% DOD
Lead-acid	0.001 - 50	0.1 - 100	s - h	ms	0.033 - 0.3	min - days	70-90	5-15	400 - 1500
Ni-Cd	0.01 - 40	10 ⁻⁵ - 1.5	s - h	ms	0.067 - 0.6	min - days	60-73	10-20	1000 - 1500
Ni-MH	0.01 - 1	10 ⁻⁵ - 0.5	h	ms	0.4 - 1.2	min - days	70-75	5-10	800 - 1200
Li-ion	0.1 - 50	10 ⁻⁵ - 100	min - h	ms	0.1 - 0.3	min - days	85-95	5-15	2000 - 5000+

Battery technology	Power density (W/L)	Specific Power (W/kg)	Energy Density (Wh/L)	Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	Capital Costs		Technological maturity
					Power (\$/kW)	Energy (\$/kWh)	
Lead-acid	10-700	75-415	50-90	20-50	300-600	200-400	Mature
Ni-Cd	75-700	100-300	60-150	40-75	500-1500	800-1500	Comercial – Mature
Ni-MH	500-3000	200-1500	140-300	45-80	600-1800	960-1800	Comercial – Mature
Li-ion	1300-10000	150-2000	200-500	70-250	1200-4000	600-2500	Comercial

Table 1. Technical requirements of conventional batteries for 2ndlife applications

Currently, two types of batteries coexist mainly in different stages of development. On the one hand, there is lead acid technology, which is a mature technology that has reached a point of evolution where it has stagnated and, therefore, its potential for improvement has been reduced. Lithium-ion technology, on the other hand, is in an incipient stage, but due to its great potential for improvement in the future and the great benefits it will bring to its customers, it is known that

it will gradually replace lead-acid batteries. Even so, during the transition time between one technology and another there will be some applications that will begin to apply the new technology earlier, especially in those vehicles that are lighter and less complex. In the case of forklifts, the introduction of lithium-ion technology will take place in several stages, with lighter trucks introducing lithium batteries before counterbalanced trucks, for example.

Regarding battery power, lithium-ion technology has made a big difference from its lead-acid predecessor. The concept of energy density designates the amount of energy that is accumulated in a specific space, and in the case of lead acid technology, the energy density (in Wh/L or Wh/Kg) is low. In contrast, lithium-ion technology has a high energy density, and is higher than that of lead acid technology and even that of nickel-metal hydroxide technology, which is used in some types of forklift trucks. In the same way, lithium batteries have had a great improvement in terms of efficiency. Lithium-ion technology has a total efficiency rating of 85% - 95%, with 5 % - 15 % energy savings compared to lead-acid technology, whose degree is between 70 % - 90 %. The degree of overall performance of the batteries translates into the amount of energy losses, so while lead acid technology has many energy losses, lithium-ion technology significantly reduces losses and increases efficiency.

On the other hand, when comparing two different technologies that are applied in batteries, it is necessary to consider the energy profile and their useful life. Regarding the energy profile, this concept refers to the state of charge of the battery in relation to use and charging times. Lithium-ion technology has revolutionized these properties. They have a higher state of charge and allow faster charges. The capacity of the battery allows the same operating periods as the lead acid battery, but with a lower nominal capacity thanks to a greater depth of discharge and energy efficiency. In addition, and by performing effective intermediate charges, charging is achieved faster than discharge and, thus, lithium-ion batteries may never empty.

In lithium technology, a 50% charge might be achieved in 30 minutes, allowing half battery to be charged in a break and facilitating work organization. To fully charge the battery only 80 minutes might be needed, thus eliminating a battery replacement and the expensive infrastructure, equipment, and downtime that this replacement requires in acid-lead technology. The concept of the energy profile of batteries is closely related to the useful lifetime of energy accumulators, which is understood as the number of life cycles that a battery has. Lead-acid batteries have an average 1,200 cycles lifetime, and lithium-ion technology offers a longer service life that exceeds up to 3 times that of lead-acid batteries, with an average life of 3,000 - 3,500 cycles. Thanks to its reduced wear, lithium technology allows intermediate charges to be carried out without wasting a battery cycle each time they are charged. Thus, while a truck needs between 2 or 3 lead-acid batteries in a lifetime, a single Lithium battery may last all truck's lifetime.

Once some of the many advantages of Li-ion batteries over other conventional storage technologies have been abovementioned, the following requirements are defined in Table 2:

2 nd -life application	Power ratio (MW)	Capacity (Discharge time)	Response time	Specific Requirements
Time Shifting	10 - 1000+	1 - 24+ h	min	Very low self-discharge rate
Stationary Energy Storage	10 - 1000+	1 - 24+ h	min	Minimum self-discharge rate
Renewable Energy Integration	0.1 - 10+	min - h	< 1 s	Compatible with the power/energy generation
Transmission and Distribution	10 - 100+	1 - 6 h	min	-
Grid Regulation	1 - 10+	ms - min	ms	-
Energy/Power management	0.1 - 1+	1 - 24+ h	min	High Peak versus Valley electricity price
Energy/Power Quality	0.01 - 1	ms - min	ms	Scalable according to power and installation characteristics
Energy/Power Reliability (Back-up)	0.1 - 10	min - h	< 1s	-
Integration of distributed renewable energy	0.01 - 0.1	1 - 6 h	< 1s	High electricity purchase rate and Low grid injection rate
e-Mobility	0.05	s - h	ms - s	High energy density and specific energy

Table 2. Technical requirements according to 2nd-life batteries applications

4. Guidelines and requirements for 2nd life use in circular economy

In this chapter the requirements for each 2nd life application and the guidelines to fulfil them are provided.

4.1 Guidelines and requirements from designing perspective.

After the path followed by the EV battery shown in figure 1, in order to design the new battery pack for the second applications, the first step would be to analyse the SoH of the whole battery, the modules and cells.

Therefore, there are different possibilities:

- The battery doesn't have any module damage and can be used.
- Only some of the modules are good enough to perform in a second application.
- Just the cells individually can be reuse.

One of the main objectives of the MARBEL Project is to design a modular battery that can be easy to dismantle even at cell level. This is because nowadays it is difficult to disassembly them or even the modules must be broken to get the cells that are still useful.

In these cases, the modules are finally disposed because it is not cost effective to recover the cell and is cheaper to buy a new one.

The next figure shows a decision tree that helps to decide whether it can be reused the whole battery, the modules or just the cells for a second life application. If there are components no longer useful, they must be properly disposed.

Figure 11. Decision tree for the second life application of reused parts

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Once the battery has been characterized, the next step is to analyse the second life application listed in chapter 3. There will be key information that must be define, such as:

- **The storage capacity:** it will determine the number of batteries or modules that will be reused and help to size the storage space.
- **Environmental condition:** this is also an important requirement. For example, if the new application is a storage container in the desert, the high temperature will affect the correct performance of the battery, so it must be properly refrigerated.
- **Portable:** is the application intended to be permanent or portable? In this case, not only the portable components will be considered but also the safety ones. For instance, the batteries or modules will need to be properly fixed so they can't be damage during the transfer.
- **Tightness:** will the application be under weather adversities? If so, the tightness of the container must be considered.
- **Residential application:** for safety reason, if the storage is in a domestic application, it will have to be prepared for non-professional user.
- **Capacity or potential storage:** depending on the purpose of the storage, the architecture will be different.
- **Mechanical loads:** the new application could be under mechanical loads. In this case, the structure of the storage must be designed considering it.

When the SoH of the battery and the requirements for the second life application have been defined, the final step would be to design the structure for holding the battery.

The rack structures are the most common way for stationary storage. The following picture shows one. Particularly, this is a battery back-up service.

Figure 12. Battery storage Source: www.ljselectric.com

In the previous example, the batteries are design for this purpose. In the case of a second life application, the rack structure will be the one designed to be adapted for holding the whole battery or the modules.

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The next figure is a conceptualized design of a rack structure for a second life application of the MARBEL battery, where the whole battery is reused and some modules to comply with the capacity requirements.

Figure 13. Rack structure for second life application Source: Eurecat

There will be also other components reused such as cables, sensors, connectors, etc. This structure will be placed in a room that could be fixed (brick building) or portable (metal containers). The following figure is an example of a metal container located in a renewable energy station.

Figure 14. Energy storage. Source: <https://www.mayfield.energy>

This type of container is common for these applications. They are fully equipped with the control system, heating or cooling system apart from other safety functionalities (see next picture).

Battery Energy Storage System

Figure 15. Battery Energy Storage System. Source: <https://www.innoliaenergy.com/>

There are also smaller applications. For instance, the household storage mentioned before. In this case the cage must be more subtle and suitable for holding in a house. For safety reason it must be tightness and can't be open by users.

The next picture is an example of a battery for domestic purpose developed by TESLA and currently available to buy.

Figure 16. Home battery from TESLA. Source. www.tesla.es

Therefore, the key point of the modular, easy to assembly and disassembly Marbel battery is to make it cost effective against new batteries so they can be reused in a second life application like the ones showed before.

Reusing the components still useful and recycling the ones that can't be reused, make the battery more circular than the current available in the market.

4.2 Guidelines and requirements from manufacturing perspective

The battery development shall be focused on the workability and rework-ability of the components to allow their reuse, second life and recyclability. The components in the battery and modules shall allow the dismantling and maintenance of the battery without damaging and compromising functionality of the components. After a clear definition of all the components that could be reusable and/or recyclable the design of the overall battery and of the components shall apply all the features and measures able to maximize the rework-ability. Process and product countermeasures shall be applied to reach the target.

4.2.1 Components reuse

Each component of the battery shall be selected/designed in such way that once disassembled no damage appears on the component itself and/or on the system. For instance, the battery cells and modules shall be removable without mechanically or electrically compromising their primary functions, so that they may be salvaged, in their entirety to be immediately used without additional processes. The development of reversible joining technologies into the HVBS is important to reach this target.

4.2.2 Electronic units

To allow a second use of components the electronic units shall not be integrated in the components and shall be easily removed and substituted. The average life of an electronic device is usually shorter than the component where it is applied and after the component dismantling the electronic is probably obsolete. The interfaces of the electronic units (geometrical, electrical, and physical) shall be standard, to be compatible with other devices and other applications.

4.2.3 Cooling system

The cooling system shall be designed to be easily emptied before the disassembly and maintenance operations. Its removal should be independent from that of other components. The reduction of the risk to have liquid coolant during battery disassembly shall improve the safety of the operators that will handle the HVBS after its operative life.

4.2.4 Sub-assembly

The design of the battery and of the components shall be focused to decrease the time and the number of the needed operations for assembly and disassembly. This goal can be reached with a reduction of the design complexity and of the number of the parts to be assembled. This can be further enhanced by intruding operations that can be performed in parallel. Sub-groups shall be introduced in the design phase to have operations in parallel to the main assembly flow. All the subgroups shall be compatible with the maximum weight and dimension and all the ergonomic requirements.

4.2.5 Covers/components connection

For an easy removal and dismantling no component shall be installed on the hidden/internal side of covers. Component installation on the exterior/visible side is allowed. It is recommended to have covers and service door as stand-alone parts.

4.3 Proposal of requirements for MARBEL 2nd life application

4.3.1 Current benchmarks for domestic energy storage systems

In order to select the layout of the system that will be built in MARBEL for second life application, it is worth to consider what is currently available in the market of the PV storage systems for domestic use and what is the direction that the market will take in the next 5 years.

The table below shows the key parameters of photovoltaic storage systems currently available on the market for domestic use.

They are systems with a nominal voltage of 48V, but higher voltage systems are rapidly establishing themselves to accommodate requests for greater power and storage capacity in the domestic storage applications. The voltage increase is also associated with a cost reduction as component that operate in voltage range of domestic application are cheaper thanks to their extensive use worldwide.

Battery Storage Parameter	Tesla POWER WALL	LG Chem RESU 48V	Pylontech 48V	Greensun Solar HV Battery
Battery DC Voltage	50 V	50 V	51.2 V	96V, 192V or 360V
DC Power, peak (10s)	7.8 kW (charge and discharge)	7 kW at 3s (charge and discharge)	5kW at 15s (charge and discharge)	6.67kW, 16.8 kW and 31.5 kW
Real DC Power, max continuous	6 kW (charge and discharge)	5 kW (charge and discharge)	2.5 kW (charge and discharge)	not specified
Maximum DC current, peak (10s)	200 A	135 A	100 A (15s)	100 A (charge and discharge)
DC current, max continuous	125 A	125 A	50 A (max continuous)	not specified
Battery Capacity	280 Ah	252 Ah	50 Ah	4X25Ah
Total Energy	14 kWh	13.1 kWh	from 2,4 kWh up to 21.6 kWh	9.6kWh, 19.2kWh or 36kWh
Usable Energy	13.5 kWh	12.4 kWh	2.2 kWh	7680Wh, 15360Wh or 28800Wh
Weight	114 kg (251.3 lbs)	99 kg	starting to 24 kg up to 220kg	200Kg, 400Kg and 640Kg
Dimensions	1150 mm x755 mm x147 mm	452mm x626mm x272mm	442mm x 410mm x 89mm	not specified
Efficiency	85-90%	85-90%	85-90%	85-90%
Electrical configuration	unknown	unknown	unknown	30s4p, 60s4p and 115s4p
cooling	Air/liquid	Air	Air	Air

Table 3. Technical requirements of some domestic photovoltaic storage systems.

4.3.2 Requirement Proposal for MARBEL battery 2nd life application

The following considerations are based on the hypothesis regarding the use in a second life of the MARBEL battery modules in an End-User application and their Integration of distributed renewable energies. The intended application is a domestic storage system for PV energy.

Table 4 shows the assumed characteristics of the cell which is currently intended to be use in MARBEL project in end of life (EOL) conditions (SoH 75%). This condition will be also the starting state of the cell for the second life application.

CATL Cell parameter @ EOL	Value
Cell Capacity (EOL)	112,5 Ah
Cell Nominal Voltage	3,7 V
Cell Energy (EOL)	420 Wh
Cell Weight	2.28 kg
Maximum DC current (EOL) peak (10s)	500 A
DC Rint (EOL)	1.2 mΩ
Module configuration	6s1p

Table 4. MARBEL cell parameters @ EOL of the first life.

After the analysis done in this document is clear the convenience of reusing the module as it is (current assumed cell configuration: 6s1p). This will reduce the need for rework, especially when the cooling system is maintained.

Depending on the module availability after testing and the market tendency in the next years, MARBEL will assemble and integrate one of configurations listed in Table 5. The main drivers of the selection will be the intended storage capacity (current proposals range from 7.5 to 20 kWh) and the maximum allowed voltage (currently not exceeding 110 V of the American public AC grid for efficiency reasons).

The proposed capacity is aligned with that of the products available in the market, while the voltage is proposed to reflect a tendency that will be probably confirmed in the near future.

The proposed electrical configurations are sufficient to fulfill a common domestic power demand and to guarantee an autonomy from the public network from 2 up to 6 hours.

Battery storage parameters	18s1p configuration	18s2p configuration	24s1p configuration	24s2p configuration
Battery Nominal Voltage	67.14 V	67.14 V	89.5 V	89.5 V
Battery EOL residual Capacity	112.5 Ah	225Ah	112.5 Ah	225Ah
Battery Total Energy	7.5 kWh	15 kWh	10 kWh	20 kWh
Battery Usable Energy (DOD 80%)	6 kWh	12 kWh	8 kWh	16 kWh
Maximum Battery Power (1C-rate)	7.3 kW	14 kW	9.7 kW	19.4 kW
Continuous Battery Power (0.7C-rate)	5 kW	9.8 kW	6.8 kW	13.6 kW
Battery Weight	62 kg	118 kg	80 kg	152 kg
Battery Self Heating (max)	275 W	550 W	365 W	730 W

Table 5. Technical requirements of 4 different proposal for a MARBEL domestic photovoltaic storage system.

5. Conclusions

Second life of EV batteries is under research from several points of view since in the coming years a large amount of used EV batteries will be available in the market. These batteries will no longer be useful for the automotive sector but they may have applications in other sectors. The extended use phase of these batteries may reduce the environmental impact and become a more cost-effective approach to the electrification of other sectors and help reduce the effect of climate change and the impact of human activities in the environment.

In this report the status and pathways of the batteries when they have reached their end of life is studied and a summary provided. The different applications for 2nd life uses are analysed in detail and those results are linked to the activities that have to be undergone to actually provide a feasible extended use phase for those batteries until the recycling process is activated in order to close the circular economy loop. Recycling activities are described in detail in D2.5 from this project.

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